

HETEROPOLY ACIDS OF NIOBIUM AND TANTALUM WITH IODIC AND PERIODIC ACIDS

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The preparation and properties of some heteropoly acids of niobium and tantalum with iodic and periodic acids have been described. Their composition can be represented by the general formula, R_2O_{5-1} or $2 HIO_3(HIO_4) \cdot xH_2O$; where $R = Nb$ or Ta .

Niobium and tantalum have been found to give various complexes with oxalic acid (Russ, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1902, **31**, 42) and tartaric acid (Srinivasan, *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1950, **31A**, 194). Formation of complexes with catechol, pyrogallol, salicylic acid, salicylaldehyde, acetylacetone (Rosenheim and Roehrich, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, **204**, 342); 8-hydroxyquinoline (Süe, *Compt. rend.*, 1933, **196**, 1022); phenol, β -naphthol etc. (Funk and Baumann, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1937, **231**, 264) has also been reported. Insoluble complex compounds of hypophosphorous acid with niobium and tantalum have been described by Alimarin and Burova (*J. Appl. Chem. USSR.*, 1945, **18**, 286). Uspenskya and Chernikov (*Compt. rend. Acad. Sci., USSR.*, 1940, **28**, 800) claim to have separated Nb and Ta by precipitating Ta from its oxalato complex by the addition of iodic acid. The exact composition of the complex has not, however, been given.

The neighbours of Nb and Ta in the IV group of the Periodic Table, such as Ti, Zr and Th, all are known to give simple and double iodates. Similarly molybdenum and tungsten of the VI group also give rise to complex heteropoly acids with iodic acid. It is also well known that vanadium, the lower homologue of Nb and Ta, forms various heteropoly acids with iodic and periodic acids (Rosenheim and Yang, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1923, **129**, 181).

It was therefore considered interesting to examine whether Nb and Ta too formed heteropoly acid complexes of a similar type. With this end in view, an attempt was made to prepare the iodates and periodates of Nb and Ta following the method of Rây and Saha (*ibid.*, 1932, **208**, 100), employed for the preparation of titani-iodates. This has led to the preparation of the following compounds:

1. $Nb_2O_5 \cdot 2HIO_3 \cdot 2H_2O (Nb_2O_5 \cdot I_2O_5 \cdot 3H_2O)$.
2. $Nb_2O_5 \cdot 2HIO_4 \cdot 8H_2O (Nb_2O_5 \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot 9H_2O)$.
3. $Ta_2O_5 \cdot HIO_3 \cdot 6H_2O (2Ta_2O_5 \cdot I_2O_5 \cdot 13H_2O)$.
4. $Ta_2O_5 \cdot 2HIO_4 \cdot 2H_2O (Ta_2O_5 \cdot I_2O_7 \cdot 3H_2O)$.

All these compounds lose most of their water molecules at about 110° — 115° retaining only those necessary for their constitution as indicated above by the first mode of formulating their composition. They are therefore best represented as complex heteropoly acids of the structure:

On this basis, iodato-niobic acid (1) and periodato-niobic and tantallic acids (2 and 4) become binuclear heteropoly acids with an oxygen bridge, and iodato-tantallic acid forms mononuclear heteropoly acid, with quinquivalent and septivalent iodine as the central atom in the iodato- and periodato-acids respectively. The co-ordination number of iodine in these heteropoly acids is six with the oxygen atoms occupying one or two positions each. All the substances are acidic to litmus and liberate iodine from potassium iodide solution even without the addition of any acid, which indicates that they are really acids.

Alternatively, they may be regarded as derivatives of ortho-iodic and ortho-periodic acids as shown below :

EXPERIMENTAL

Iodato-niobic Acid.—Iodic acid was dissolved in nitric acid (1:1) and added dropwise to a filtered solution of potassium niobifluoride in 50% nitric acid with constant stirring. This was taken in a platinum basin and was warmed on the water-bath. A white milky precipitate was formed, which was thoroughly stirred with a platinum spatula. The mixture was warmed on the bath till all the hydrofluoric acid was removed. A white crystalline precipitate settled down; this was cooled and washed four to five times with nitric acid (1:1) by decantation to free it from any fluoride ion. The product was then filtered through a sintered glass funnel and washed thoroughly with 50% nitric acid solution. The substance was dried in a desiccator over sulphuric acid and potassium hydroxide.

The substance forms a white powder, insoluble in water and also in organic solvents. On heating, it gives off violet vapours of iodine. A suspension of the substance in water liberates iodine from potassium iodide solution. It is acidic to litmus.

Niobium was estimated by igniting the compound in a platinum crucible and weighing as Nb_2O_5 . The iodate was estimated by treating the substance with a solution of potassium iodide and acetic acid, and titrating the liberated iodine with standard thiosulphate solution. [Found : Nb, 28.37 ; IO_3 , 53.24 ; H_2O (by loss at $110^\circ - 115^\circ$), 5.49. $Nb_2O_5 \cdot 2HIO_3 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires Nb, 28.40 ; IO_3 , 53.51 ; H_2O , 5.50 per cent]. [Found (dried at $110^\circ - 115^\circ$.): Nb, 30.02 ; IO_3 , 56.60. $Nb_2O_5 \cdot 2HIO_3$ requires Nb, 30.05 ; IO_3 , 56.63 per cent].

Periodato-niobic acid was prepared from a solution of potassium periodate in 50% nitric acid and that of potassium niobifluoride in the same acid following the method described above. The substance resembles the iodato-niobic acid in all its properties.

Periodate ion was estimated by titrating with standard thiosulphate, the iodine liberated by the substance from acidified potassium iodide. [Found : Nb, 23.37 ; IO_4 , 48.15 ; H_2O (by loss at $110^\circ - 115^\circ$), 18.18. $Nb_2O_5 \cdot 2HIO_4 \cdot 8H_2O$ requires Nb, 23.40 ; IO_4 , 48.10 ; H_2O , 18.13 per cent].

[Found (dried at $110^\circ - 115^\circ$.): Nb, 28.63 ; IO_4 , 58.79. $Nb_2O_5 \cdot 2HIO_4$ requires Nb, 28.60 ; IO_4 , 58.77 per cent].

Iodato-tantallic acid was prepared exactly like the the corresponding niobium compound using potassium tantalifluoride in place of potassium niobifluoride.

The substance forms a white powder, and resembles the corresponding niobium compound in properties. [Found : Ta, 49.87 ; IO_3 , 24.12 ; H_2O (by loss at $110^\circ - 115^\circ$), 14.89. $Ta_2O_5 \cdot HIO_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ requires Ta, 49.86 ; IO_3 , 24.10 ; H_2O , 14.87 per cent].

[Found (dried at $110^\circ - 115^\circ$.): Ta, 58.59 ; IO_3 , 28.33. $Ta_2O_5 \cdot HIO_3$ requires Ta, 58.57 ; IO_3 , 28.32 per cent].

Periodato-tantallic acid was prepared exactly like the corresponding niobium compound using potassium tantalifluoride in place of potassium niobifluoride. It resembles its niobium analogue in properties. [Found : Ta, 41.95 ; IO_4 , 44.33 ; H_2O (by loss at $110^\circ - 115^\circ$), 4.15. $Ta_2O_5 \cdot 2HIO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ requires Ta, 41.99 ; IO_4 , 44.31 ; H_2O , 4.19 per cent].

[Found (dried at $110^\circ - 115^\circ$.): Ta, 43.81 ; IO_4 , 46.26. $Ta_2O_5 \cdot 2HIO_4$ requires Ta, 43.82 ; IO_4 , 46.24 per cent].